

Intervention Follows Diagnosis: The Impact of Analysis on the Urban Regeneration of Open Spaces in Mass Housing Estates

Diagnosis and design are part of the same process. This statement is particularly true for urban regeneration efforts, in which the way that complex obsolescence processes are understood implies a particular design method. In the specific case of the regeneration of mass housing estates, most experiences are approached from the building perspective. Even though open spaces are central to ensuring a high degree of urban quality, urban regeneration projects often fail to recognise the problems and opportunities relating to their layout. The aim of this paper is to discuss the relevance of incorporating pertinent open space diagnoses into integrated urban regeneration efforts in mass housing estates. To this end, the paper explores in depth three different experiences of urban regeneration in Spain.

Keywords: Integrated urban regeneration, public space, urban analysis

L'intervento segue la diagnosi: l'impatto dell'analisi sulla rigenerazione urbana degli spazi aperti nei quartieri residenziali moderni

La diagnosi e la progettazione sono parte dello stesso processo. La validità di quest'affermazione appare evidente nelle operazioni di rigenerazione urbana dove il modo di comprendere i complessi processi di obsolescenza determina un certo modo di progettare. Benché nella rigenerazione dei quartieri residenziali moderni gli spazi aperti siano essenziali per garantire un'elevata qualità urbana, la maggior parte degli interventi riguarda quasi esclusivamente gli edifici. Di solito i progetti di rigenerazione di questi quartieri trascurano non solo i problemi che presentano ma anche le opportunità che offrono. Da questo studio emerge la necessità di implementare una diagnosi appropriata degli spazi aperti nei quartieri residenziali moderni prima di affrontare le operazioni di rigenerazione urbana. Il presente articolo prende in esame tre casi dell'esperienza spagnola che contribuiscono a illustrare la tesi proposta.

Parole chiave: Rigenerazione urbana integrata, spazio pubblico, analisi urbana

On the importance of diagnosis in integrated urban regeneration efforts

«Schemes, however, are in incubation, alike by municipal officials, by public utility associations, and by private individuals, expert or otherwise, which, whatever their particular merits, are not based upon any sufficient surveys of the past development and present conditions of their towns, nor upon adequate knowledge of good and bad town planning elsewhere. In such cases the natural order, that of town survey before town planning, is being reversed; and in this way individuals and public bodies are in danger of committing themselves to plans which would have been widely different with fuller knowledge; yet which, once produced, it will be too late to replace, and even difficult to modify.»
(Geddes, 1915: 345)

At the beginning of the last century, Patrick Geddes, with the publication of *Cities in Evolution* (1915), advocated an urban planning approach under the motto ‘*survey before planning*’, which recognised the need to conduct diagnosis prior to urban interventions. Even though analysis methods have evolved since then, two reflections included in his text are still relevant. The first is related to the idea of how certain diagnoses influence different types of intervention, that is, the way in which the problems and opportunities of cities and urban environments are understood impacts the way in which they are acted upon. In the second reflection, the need for robust diagnoses is underscored as a measure to guarantee that resources are correctly optimised. The starting point for this paper is the concept of ‘intervention follows diagnosis’, since analysis implies the beginning of understanding and helps when putting forward proposals. Deep down, as some authors claim, diagnosis and design are part of the same process (Strappa, 2018).

Based on this foundation, the model of the ‘functional city’ of the International Congresses of Modern Architecture (CIAM) and the Athens Charter should be understood as a response to a diagnosis focused on the idea of congestion and unhealthy conditions that characterised the urban fabrics at that time (Van Es *et al.*, 2015). The

response to this diagnosis that reported the failure of the traditional city was the commitment to the design of the open city, an alternative model of healthy, sunny and egalitarian cities. These ideas became a reality during the post-World War II period in the so-called mass housing estates, an urban development model that has shaped new heterogeneous landscapes (Monclús and Díez Medina, 2016; Rowlands *et al.*, 2009).

One of the main contributions that mass housing estates brought to modern life was ‘open space’ as an alternative to the streets and squares model of the traditional city (Díez Medina and Monclús, 2020). Closely related to the concept of ‘public space’, this paper deals with the notion of ‘open space’ understood as the remaining space between the towers and slabs of the modernist city. The meaning of ‘open space’ does not refer to a single pattern of use, form or management, but includes a range of different nature (parks, squares and inter-slab spaces) and management (public, private, or ambiguous spaces). Although this modern utopia was promising—open space provided sunshine and healthy conditions to residential buildings while increasing the public land used for leisure—the legacy left by the actual urban planning of this space has not been free from criticism (Díez Medina, 2015; Turkington *et al.*, 2004). Several voices have reported the deficiencies and questionable operation of these spaces, either due to problems related to their poor urban quality, a lack of definition or lack of management and maintenance.

Despite the criticism, it is important to also recognise the opportunities that open space provides for the regeneration of housing estates (García-Pérez *et al.*, 2020; Sotoca, 2012). On the one hand, due to their inherent features—since they are planned buildings—they generally have a large amount of available free space. On the other hand, they have undeniable heritage value, beyond their classification according to architectural quality (Docomomo International, 2018). Housing estates are considered to

be the most important living legacy of functionalist urban planning, with a fundamental historical role in resolving the housing deficit that characterised the European post-war period (Pendlebury *et al.*, 2009).

In contrast to the large number of rehabilitation experiences approached from the technical or building perspective, only a few have identified the opportunity in open space layout, which is likely due, in part, to the difficulty involved in identifying the problems and opportunities that stem from the design. However, focusing on these open spaces is of the utmost importance when it comes to defining urban regeneration strategies to promote more compact, vital, safe and inclusive cities—in line with the sustainable development objectives set out by the new international urban planning agenda (United Nations, 2015).

According to the initial idea set out at the beginning of this text, the hypothesis that could explain the unbalanced attention usually given to these types of spaces is the lack of accurate diagnoses that properly identify the problems and opportunities their design entails. As a result of the complexity of such interventions, accurate diagnoses are essential prior to designing urban regeneration strategies, processes and projects. To verify the idea, it is interesting to study the relationship between such diagnoses and the interventions performed.

Therefore, the aim of the paper is to discuss the relevance of incorporating pertinent open space diagnoses into integrated urban regeneration projects in mass housing estates.¹ In this regard, the paper first explores the relationship between the

¹ Although this paper focuses on the physical dimension of open spaces, integrated urban regeneration is understood as those processes in which physical actions (on buildings and on open spaces) as well as social and economic actions are framed in a coordinated approach over space and time, with a single purpose: to reverse the processes of decline in

problems accumulated by housing estates and their relation to the promotion of greater urban quality. Then, the text reviews the relationships between the problems detected in several international experiences, and the interventions proposed to verify the interest of the hypothesis. Specifically, the paper explores three experiences of rehabilitation and regeneration of Spanish housing estates, to verify more fully how the different approaches to understanding the problems and opportunities of open spaces have influenced the interventions performed. In fact, this analysis allows us to understand how the understanding of the problems and opportunities of free spaces is related to the way in which solutions are proposed. Therefore, a deeper understanding of them could contribute to generating open spaces of higher urban quality.

The importance of open space layout for the quality of housing estates

The influence of open space layout on the quality of housing estates has been part of a debate addressed in urban planning literature. Richard Sendi's paper (2009) recognises two opposing attitudes relating to this fact. The first, called 'physical determinism', assumes that modifying the physical form can cause changes in social behaviours. In contrast to the first reflections made from the perspective of security (Newman, 1972), there are other visions today that—from the perspective of urban design—recognise that the physical dimension can favour social and economic improvement (Gehl *et al.*, 2006; Urban Task Force, 1999). The second attitude, the 'liberal approach', accentuates the criticism of design errors on these spaces and promotes, as design criterion, not imposing limitations on users (Jacobs, 1961; Sendra, 2016).

areas of significant territorial vulnerability (García-Pérez, 2017; Monclús, 2018; Moya González and Díez de Pablo, 2012).

Despite the strengths and limitations of these stances, they both support the impact that open space design has on the quality of housing estates. Carmona recently supported this idea by confirming the critical role that open space design plays in new building projects and in those that promote the urban regeneration of the existing city (Carmona, 2019). This approach has also been recognised by the institutional framework that promotes urban regeneration, both at a European (EU Ministers for Urban Development, 2007) and international level (UN-Habitat, 2015).

In his paper, Carmona reflects on which principles of quality open space should be promoted in urban regeneration efforts—evolving, diverse, free, delineated, engaging, meaningful, social, balanced, comfortable and robust. Table 1 relates these quality principles with the problems that arise in the open spaces of housing estates. It has been developed by identifying the physical problems associated with public spaces using a systematic review of the literature through the works of Hall (1997), Turkington *et al.* (2004) and Wassenberg (2013), in the European scene, and Moya (1983), Ferrer i Aixalá (1996) and García Vázquez *et al.* (2016), in the Spanish scene.

The problems resulting from functionalist principles are remarkable. The lack of metropolitan connectivity and physical isolation, partly caused by the principles of self-sufficiency; the lack of functional diversity, due to the rigid separation of functions; and the incorporation of a new open space criteria, sometimes uncontrollable and undefined due to the lack of relationship between the buildings and the street system. Additionally, regarding the economic use of resources, the ideas of serialisation and standardization have an effect of impersonality and trivialisation of space. These authors also recognise problems in management, above all with regard to the late incorporation of facilities and urbanisation of the housing estate, or the general lack of care for the built environment. Finally, they recognise a problem of adaptation of these characteristics to the new urban

demands. Specifically, the widespread use of the car lead to a parking problem which ultimately affected the quality of the open spaces. Ambiguity over building density has also had an effect over time on the lack of urban intensity. Below is an analysis of the influence of each of the problems relating to the quality principles proposed by Carmona.

Addressing the metropolitan connectivity issues of some housing estates by removing physical barriers, increasing spatial connectivity and improving alternative transport systems helps to improve accessibility (covered under the principle of adequate ‘delineation’), which is important for quality public spaces. Improving connectivity can also result in improving movement flows, which clearly addresses the basic principle of promoting ‘social relationships’.

Improving the conditions of diversity of uses, particularly in housing estates with a high deficit of activities and services, results in a greater ability of public spaces to ‘attract’; additionally, the design of a physical support to promote diverse and adaptable activities is also related to the principle of ‘robustness’.

Addressing the problem of trivialisation and the alienating nature of some open spaces means accepting diversity in design. The ‘one size fits all’ philosophy ceases to be valid, since it does not provide the diversity, continuity and meaning that characterise quality open space.

The poor quality in the urbanisation of some housing estates should be improved in order to ensure, first, the promotion of comfortable and safe spaces—by providing opportunities to walk, rest and converse consistent with human nature—and, second, that urbanisation responds to a simple design that adapts to changes in context in the short, medium and long term.

Quality public space should promote an adequate balance between space for pedestrians and space for vehicles. Although housing estates were initially developed with an effort to separate vehicles and pedestrians, the increase in the number of users has changed the original design of some of them (Pérez-Igualada, 2017). In addition, shared space solutions—with pedestrian priority—are more beneficial to promoting urban quality compared to strict separation.

Density influences urban vitality. Open spaces should have adequate proportions in terms of built surface and planned functions in order to act as catalysts for social concentration and intensity, a basic principle of quality open space (Delclòs-Alió and Miralles-Guasch, 2018).

Ensuring that open spaces are well-maintained results in a greater feeling of security, a basic characteristic of the principle of ‘comfort’. Likewise, improving the definition of how to use and manage semi-public spaces, which characterise many housing estates, will lead to greater understanding of the management and ownership of open space.

Improving the accessibility, diversity, intensity and ambiguity problems that some open spaces in housing estates develop to a greater or lesser extent involves focusing on the layout of said spaces, beyond providing adequate maintenance and upkeep. Accepting the importance of considering open space in urban regeneration experiences within a process of integrated actions is essential.

Table 1. Insert here

Intervention follows diagnosis

Based on the idea that certain diagnoses imply a specific type of intervention, this text analyses, firstly, the influence of diagnoses on several efforts that have

promoted the regeneration of housing estates and, secondly, the details of the diagnoses and proposals of three experiences in Spain.

From diagnosis to intervention

Demolition, adaptation or upgrading can be understood as three different responses (either individually or combined) to a specific initial diagnosis that assesses the degree of morphological adaptability necessary to promote urban improvement. The analysis of some European regeneration models reveals a wide range of diagnoses, from those that focus on the failure of the open city model to those that have identified the values of this urban form and its opportunities for transformation.²

The paradigmatic case of Bijlmermeer is one of the diagnoses that focus on the failure of the modernist housing estate urban design model. The analyses carried out since the 1990s³ considered the physical layout of Bijlmermeer to be «[...] a *fundamental mistake in urban design: too massive, with too much high-rise and especially having too little differentiation in the housing stock*» (Helleman and Wassenberg, 2004: 7). However, the failure of the urban design—partly due to the rigidity of the planning model adopted for an area of 600 hectares—also entailed an economic failure, since it was impossible to create a neighbourhood that attracted the real estate market. The diagnosis, published in 1990 under the title «*Bijlmermeer will remain, but it has to change*» (*De Bijlmer blijft, veranderen*), introduced the idea of

² The selection of the three cases reflects the need to verify the link between diagnosis and intervention in different regeneration efforts. The three cases are paradigmatic and have been widely reported in the literature. The types of transformation have recently been systematised by F. Lepratto (2017).

³ Although some proposals for Bijlmer were put forward before the 1990s, it was then that this diagnosis that challenged the earlier conservative view was made.

demolishing this modern urban fabric and adding a new urban morphology as an alternative to the ‘towers and slabs’ model. Almost 25 years after the first demolition (1995), the original complex has been reduced to a symbolic area (even after being transformed to new standards) in favour of a new, finer-grained ‘ordinary’ fabric that moves away from unit production as a mechanism for diversity (Aquilué Junyent and Roca Blanch, 2019). However, other alternatives that did identify values in the environment, without ignoring the problems related to the urban design, coexisted with this diagnosis. Specifically, the OMA proposal recognised the monumental character of Bijlmermeer and the repetition of buildings as the intrinsic values of the housing estate. For Koolhaas, the problem lay in the fact that «*the spectre of urban activities produced by the actual Bijlmermeer is too poor*» (OMA, 1986), and he blamed the physical layout for this. His proposal was based on preserving the residential slabs and promoting axes of significant urban intensity in order to provide quality to the vast amount of open space. Without criticising which of the two proposals would have been more adequate for Bijlmermeer in the long term, both demolition and intensification respond to two diagnoses that differ in their assessment of the degree of adaptability of the complex.

There are also diagnoses that have successfully identified opportunities in the functionalist city model. A good example is the work carried out by the architects Druot, Lacaton and Vassal, whose diagnosis has been published in the book ‘*Plus*’ (2007). Their analysis focused not only on the problems present in housing estates (isolation, lack of urban intensity, little attention to detail), but also on acknowledging the benefits (strength of architectural types, sanitary solutions based on good lighting and ventilation, a certain versatility and ability to transform) and the opportunities for evolution and improvement they provide (possibility of densification and intensification). For these French architects, «*the inheritance of modernism must by no*

means be seen as something complete or finished but, like every other building or urban fragment, can be appropriated by its successor» (Druot *et al.*, 2007: 21). Based on recycling the constructions, their ideas respond to their vision of housing estates as ‘an exceptional case’. They proposed solutions based on three basic principles: first, to improve habitability by redistributing and expanding the number of dwellings, which is done by superimposing new prefabricated modules; second, to improve common spaces by promoting better accessibility and social interactions; and, lastly, to improve the interaction with the ground level, by increasing the density of the ground floor in order to intensify its urban uses, thereby promoting a new public-private definition of open space. Their recent work on the Grand Parc in Bordeaux perfectly summarises their first two ideas. However, the diagnosis and interventions that Druot, Lacaton and Vassal promote should also be understood as a reaction to the National Urban Renewal Programme,⁴ which focused on the demolition, new land division and rehabilitation of existing buildings (Castrillo, 2010). The purpose of the programme recognised the concentration of vulnerable dwellings as the result of *«on the one hand, a strong specialisation in de facto and de jure social housing and, on the other, a degraded residential attractiveness, specifically due to low urban quality (mediocre public spaces, isolation, lack of facilities and services...)»*. The association of social problems with the physical dimension posits that *«urban renovation aims to transform these neighbourhoods into ‘ordinary’ urban spaces characterised by a diversity of functions and housing types, openness and relation with the rest of the city, quality of public spaces»* (ANRU, 2012). Once again, the different conclusions provided by the diagnoses for the French case study offer several solutions.

⁴ Agence Nationale pour la Rénovation Urbaine (ANRU).

Other types of diagnoses have been able to recognise both the need for transformation and the degree of adaptability of some housing estates. Poptahof, in Delft, is an example of this hybrid approach. The team of architects recognised the spatial quality of the neighbourhood, although there was a need «*to translate the original landscape quality of the residential area in a contemporary way*» (Palmbout Urban Landscapes, 2004). To do so, their diagnosis focused both on public spaces, by recognising its conservation problems and its uncontrollable character that hindered urban vitality, and on the buildings, by identifying the excessive homogeneity in the building types used and the lack of compliance with current standards, specifically those related to dimension (González González and Stouten, 2014). The proposal outlines a morphological change that generates greater social diversity by increasing the floor area ratio. This strategy allows a large part of the original residential area to be rehabilitated and new housing types to be introduced. One of the most interesting aspects is that reconsidering the floor area ratio allows a new open space layout with increased connections and hierarchy by creating urban blocks. The morphological change proposed for Poptahof is based on an accurate diagnosis of the weaknesses of the open space layout and of the opportunities for replanning. This makes it possible to develop greater urban intensity in favour of the effort's main strategy: social diversity.

Radical transformation, the recycling of constructions and mixed strategies reflect different regeneration models that have a clear impact on the layout of open space. Without assessing the final results of the proposals, it seems clear that the decision-making process for each of these models is closely related to the approach taken in their diagnoses and to the degree of adaptability of the open space assessed in each case: from considering the failure of the hard modernist urban design, which lead

to the demolition of large area of the Bijlmermeer, to detecting the restructuring opportunities of Poptahof and Grand Parc.

Three diagnoses / interventions in Spain

This section explores the relationship between diagnosis and intervention in three ground-breaking Spanish experiences representative of different forms of intervention on the heritage of functionalist urbanism. If the experience of Madrid and Zaragoza focuses more on the building dimension, and the latter also including aspects related to the recognition of heritage, the experience of Barcelona responds to a more integrated intervention, whose initial period was largely driven from the urban-building dimension. In addition, all three have been classified as ‘good practices’ according to the Dubai International Awards granted twice a year by the Spanish Habitat Committee (UN-Habitat, 2018).⁵

To carry out this study, this section focuses on a morphological analysis. Diagnosis and description of actions reports, planimetry, as well as official evaluation documents of the proposals have been consulted. Once the data was collected, a critical analysis was conducted through textual quotations from official documents, systematization of the main contributions (Table 2), as well as the development of a homogeneous type/morphological mapping of the three urban regeneration efforts (Figure 1). Although some of the experiences considered have been—or continue to be—included in urban regeneration programmes, the analysis focuses on the specific periods listed in Table 2. The interventions have been considered from a quantitative

⁵ It is worth noting that the inclusion of these cases in the 'good practices' catalogue may not be the result of exemplary work done on open space.

and qualitative point of view in order to verify the importance of open space in these efforts.

From the quantitative point of view, data on the budgets for the chosen actions have been collected.⁶ Two comparative rates have been calculated for each case: first, the rate of public investment allocated to each housing unit according to the total amount budgeted for all actions included in the building dimension and the number of housing units affected; and, second, the rate of public investment in open space calculated by relating the budget items for interventions on open space to the entire surface area included in the analysed plans. From the point of view of quality, the diagnoses and proposals have been analysed based on the physical dimension of housing, of open space and other activities of a socio-economic nature. Table 2 summarises the quantitative and qualitative information to facilitate a comparative analysis.

To better understand these interventions, it is worth noting that the Spanish context focuses on property ownership, in contrast to other European cases that focus on renting (Cortés Alcalá, 2004). This aspect mainly affects the possibility of unitary interventions. While single ownership, generally public, favours homogeneous interventions in the rest of Europe, unitary interventions in Spain are more difficult, as horizontal property arrangements are a significant administrative barrier (Musterd *et al.*, 2007). It is important to understand this limitation in order to assess interventions in an international context.

⁶ In order to homogenise the information assessed, the data collected refers to public investment made within the specific programmes analysed. In addition, the budgets for the selected cases have been updated in accordance with the CPI, given the different time frame in which the projects were carried out, taking the last year of the intervention as the reference date.

Residential obsolescence: The Integral Restoration Area of San Cristóbal de Los Ángeles, Madrid

San Cristobal de los Ángeles is one of the Spanish administration's most significant public housing developments (constructed by the *Organización de Poblados Dirigidos* in collaboration with *Instituto Nacional de la Vivienda*) (Díez de Pablo, 2015: 116). With a markedly autonomous character, it contains some 6,000 dwellings (López de Lucio *et al.*, 2016: 432). The housing estate showed signs of urban vulnerability early on, initially influenced by low building quality, as well as a high level of isolation from the rest of the urban fabric. Vulnerability has recently increased due to the high population density with low financial capacity and/or an immigrant background. Even though the area had been subject to isolated rehabilitation efforts since the 1980s, new works for improving the neighbourhood started at the beginning of the new millennium. This paper refers to the intervention included within the Integral Rehabilitation Area (ARI in Spanish) developed between 1999 and 2010 alongside the Community Development Plan (Arroyo Castillo, 2010; UN-Habitat, 2008).

Initially, the works began with two complementary diagnoses. The first, from the building dimension, detected severe building pathologies and a general lack of adaptability to current accessibility and thermal insulation standards. The second focused on open space, facilities and services. In an interview, the ARI's chief architect explained how «*as part of the study of open space, the renovation needs regarding facilities and services, urban furniture, trees, etc. were analysed*» and recognised the significant physical and functional isolation of the environment, since the location was surrounded by industrial infrastructure and areas (Mata Wagner, 2008). Almost 20 years after this diagnosis, it seems clear that this pioneering experience failed to include a deeper urban reflection that would go beyond urbanisation problems and focus on the problems of open space layout. There is no reference in the official documents to the

form of the open space, nor to the capacity of its buildings to develop greater functional and residential diversity, or even to encourage greater attention to the immediate relationship between the ground floor and buildings.

As figure 1 shows, the intervention does not significantly change in terms of urban form. The intervention—clearly directed towards residential buildings—promotes a demolition/substitution strategy for one third of the built elements, which had serious structural pathologies. The new buildings, proposed according to energy efficiency criteria, respect the initial morphology of the housing estate to a great extent. In addition, a rehabilitation strategy that financed mostly accessibility and energy efficiency operations was put forward. When the neighbours showed distrust during the initial phases of the intervention, a Community Development Plan integrating socio-economic measures to strengthen community identity and to unblock regeneration processes was commissioned. The urban measures, included within a Special Inner Reform Plan (2001), consist, essentially, in reurbanising inter-block spaces (by improving paving and urban furniture) and updating urban infrastructure. Although the Plan enabled an increase in the floor area ratio of up to 20%, in practice this measure was not harnessed to rethink open space layout, nor did it entail an increase in urban intensity.

In quantitative terms, investment in urban aspects amounts to 25% of the total, reaching an investment rate in open space of €24/m², which, according to López Lucio (2016), is an insufficient amount in proportion to the amount invested in building. The results obtained have increased the existing urbanisation quality; however, the case of San Cristóbal, with a diagnosis focused on residential building, lacks a minimum reflection on the urban design problems of housing estates. The absence of a broad diagnosis on open space that is able to identify the problems and opportunities related to

the activation of increased intensity and urban vitality by studying the open space layout has reduced the intervention to a superficial ‘makeover’.

Legacy of interest: Pilot projects for the housing estates in Zaragoza

The main experience on housing estate rehabilitation in Zaragoza falls within the framework of the ‘urban areas of interest’. In a context in which reflections on rehabilitation were more important from the point of view of urban fabrics that were both highly central and had significant heritage value, the city of Zaragoza was a pioneer in extending this concept to the outskirts of the city, focusing on areas built under the principles of functionalist urbanism. Although the most visible result came from completing the four pilot projects, the work began by carrying out a detailed study on the 21 housing estates located in the first periphery belt around the city (Ruiz Palomeque and Rubio del Val, 2006). The working methodology, which has been identified as ‘best practice’, was proposed based on the physical and social features of the functionalist post-war urban fabric in Zaragoza; this involved selecting several pilot areas that—supported by significant public investment—could be used to extrapolate the efforts.

The preliminary studies are based on the building dimension, although the social dimension is also included. From a construction standpoint, diagnosis on buildings has a greater influence. This analysis recognises problems related to habitability (minimum dimensions), stability (structural safety) and functionality (health standards, energy saving and accessibility) and promotes ‘quality building rehabilitation’, that *«updates the built heritage, that is, upgrades and/or adapts the existing buildings according to regulations for new buildings»* (Ruiz Palomeque and Rubio del Val, 2006: 88). The section that focuses on urban analysis, titled *«Diagnosis on Urbanisation and Planning»*, detected conservation issues related to the failure to define ownership, a lack

of services and parking, as well as inflexible planning for remodelling or restructuring efforts (Ruiz Palomeque and Rubio del Val, 2006: 98). A vision on open space which correctly identifies current problems, but does not explore in depth the causes, related to design and urban form, that contributed to this situation.

Based on this diagnosis, the pilot projects adapted construction to current regulatory standards, particularly in relation to energy efficiency and accessibility. However, the intervention on public spaces was reduced to simply improving urban infrastructure and reurbanisation. As figure 1 shows, there are no visible formal changes in either the plot structure or the open space layout. However, the general proposals (which were not carried out) for the housing estates from the urban point of view contemplated increasing the floor area ratio by defining movement areas for each housing estate but not a morphological modification that would allow a new layout for open space. These housing estates have been included in the preservation catalogue of the General Urban Development Plan (PGOU), acknowledging their heritage value. However, the conservation promoted by this intervention, which was designed to be positive, could be self-defeating as it limits possibilities of interventions that promote deeper morphological transformation in the medium and long term.

The budget allocation for open space amounts to 12% of the total and the investment rate in the urban dimension is €28/m². Investment in the urban dimension is also low in comparison to investment in the building dimension. Although the experience in Zaragoza recognises several urban problems, it reduces the analysis of public space to urbanisation, maintenance and planning problems. No diagnosis recognises the level of morphological adaptability of each case, the specific layout of open spaces or their opportunity for improvement. In addition, a legislative framework that favours conservation prevents future changes on land division or buildings.

Restricting these interventions could constrain actions that contribute to better delineation of open space and an increase in urban intensity and vitality.

Replanning as an opportunity: The transformation plan for La Mina neighbourhood, Barcelona

La Mina is a neighbourhood located in the municipality of Sant Adrià del Besós, close to the administrative boundary of Barcelona. Its construction was promoted through a plan for the suppression of slums between 1971-74. The estate stands out for incorporating new building typologies that respond to new prefabrication techniques (López de Lucio, 2008: 126). The process of relocating shantytowns has long marked the image of the neighbourhood. Since the 1990s, the public sector has proposed different alternatives for intervention, even considering radical demolition (Ayuntamiento de Barcelona, 2011). This analysis focuses on the processes initiated from the 2000s onwards, specifically the transformation of the so-called Special Reform and Replanning Plan, which was approved in 2004 (UN-Habitat, 2010b). The transformation of La Mina neighbourhood is an example of integrated urban regeneration in Spain. It also represents a model where the prior diagnoses proved to be essential in assessing the possibilities of transforming the neighbourhood (López de Lucio, 2008: 158).

This Plan is based on a three-pronged analysis which, from an comprehensive perspective, focuses on the social dimension (recognising crime and security issues), the building dimension (recognising that housing has good structural conditions but need to be updated to current regulations) and the urban dimension (recognising that problems such as a high proportion of open space, low spatial, social and usage diversity and isolation coexist). Opportunities such as the new relative position after flagship urban

projects such as the 2004 Forum and the 22@ technological district project and the high level of public facilities are also recognised (Cervero Sánchez and Agustín Hernández, 2015; Velázquez Valoria and Verdaguer Viana-Cárdenas, 2011). Specifically, the diagnosis identified a significant urban barrier in the central axis of facilities and services and an opportunity for replanning that would entail *«a rupture in order to generate a new urban suture. It is undoing in order to generate new living conditions; it is recycling to optimise the urban space that is ill-consolidated at source»* (Jornet et al., 2008: 166). On this occasion, the urban diagnosis does recognise the importance of the neighbourhood's morphological layout and its impact on the spatial and social diversity and on isolation.

The proposal, based on this three-pronged diagnosis, poses an urban strategy that enables the long-term creation of a new diverse urban structure, which materialises in a new connecting civic axis by remodelling the central one (Figure 1). Thus, a new land division of the central area of public facilities results in new profitable plots that provide more housing, increasing the density/intensity of the area. In contrast to the excess of open space, this strategy makes it possible to commit *«to restraint and quality, given that an excess of inadequate public space, as happens in most of these mass housing interventions, usually leads to lower quality of the project»* (Jornet, Llop and Pastor in López de Lucio, 2008: 168). On the other hand, flexible planning criteria enable a new open space layout—the civic axis—that becomes the driving force behind a new urban vitality. In parallel, rehabilitation of existing buildings is promoted and a social support programme with active investment is implemented.

The budget of La Mina is more committed to open space. Almost 50% of the aforementioned Transformation Plan was allocated to replanning open space through new land division, redevelopment and improvement of spaces for public facilities and

urban connectivity. The rate of investment in open space amounts to €235/m², which is proportionately higher than in the previous cases. Beyond the quantitative analysis, the experience of La Mina recognises the major opportunity for transformation in open spaces given their ability to promote greater social diversity from the physical dimension. Without assessing the results of this intervention, which has been both lauded and criticised, the integral diagnosis identified the specific problems and opportunities that allowed the development of a complex process of urban transformation.

Figure 1 and Table 2. Insert here

Common factors and specificities

The different responses to the diagnosis of the degree of adaptability of functionalist urban fabrics to higher quality contemporary standards is closely related to the proposals outlined. Demolition, transformation and rehabilitation are different responses that the interventions contribute (either in a single or combined form) to the analysis on the degree of adaptability of the urban form (figure 2).

The study of the cases has shown how the detection of lower levels of adaptation of open space has led to more radical strategies, based mainly on demolition as well as partial transformations, and the consequent replacement of the urban morphology (Bijlmermeer). On the other hand, other diagnoses have failed to recognise problems or opportunities presented in open space layouts. In these cases, the proposals have focused on residential rehabilitation, by promoting the morphological conservation of the urban fabric (Madrid, Zaragoza).⁷ Finally, several diagnoses have been able to

⁷ Although Madrid has used demolition as an action of regeneration, the new constructions that have replaced the previous ones retain the same morphological characteristics as their

detect problems and opportunities in a balanced way; this has led to interventions that promote transformations that combine both the morphological transformation and modification of open space (Barcelona, Delft).

A comparative analysis of the cases in Madrid, Zaragoza and Barcelona helps to recognise certain common factors in the experiences of regeneration of mass housing estates in Spain. Regarding the buildings, particular attention has been paid to adapting them to current standards in terms of accessibility and energy efficiency. The diagnoses performed have led to building renovation interventions in these three cases.

However, most significant differences are to be found when open spaces are the subject of the analysis. A comparative approach to these three experiences makes it possible to recognise how the diagnoses of open spaces in Spain tend to focus on management and conservation issues. However, there are also other types of problems that affect the configuration of the open spaces themselves which are less considered, despite the fact that this configuration plays a relevant role in providing adequate urban quality. The cases of Madrid and Zaragoza exemplify the absence of diagnoses that address the problem of the design of open spaces. The regeneration proposals mentioned, which focus on superficial redevelopment, have not allowed us to explore the opportunities for transforming these spaces in depth. In quantitative terms, the investment made in open spaces is proportionally insufficient compared to the building dimension. The case of La Mina responds to a more complete analysis and, without entering into a judgment of the results obtained in terms of social issues, promotes a gradual transformation of its urban form that could help in the urban regeneration of this housing estate.

precedents. Demolition is associated more with the inadequacy of the structure than with the demand for adaptation of the urban form and open space.

The different emphasis on observing the original sources in parallel with the actions proposed in the case studies analysed allows to verify how a specific focus on open spaces can benefit from a greater capacity to know the specific opportunities that they offer for the urban regeneration of housing estates.

Figure 2. Insert here

Conclusions

This paper contributes to the discussion on the relevance of incorporating pertinent open space diagnoses into integrated urban regeneration efforts in mass housing estates. In a context where the building-focused interventions are predominantly technical, this study has used three recent regeneration experiences to analyse the role that open spaces play in determining the quality of housing estates and the responsibility of these diagnoses, which tend to pay less attention to these spaces.

From the observation of the relationship between the problems accumulated by housing estates and principles of urban quality, it is possible to observe how open spaces are key elements and their design is responsible, to a great extent, for the urban quality of these urban areas. Detecting and acting on both the problems and opportunities of open space layouts will help to create more inclusive, safe and vibrant cities.

After admitting the importance of open space within the integrated policy that should be promoted in urban regeneration interventions for housing estates, the paper assesses whether the emphasis placed on certain issues during the diagnosis phase has been an influential factor in the design of plans, processes and projects.

One of the key issues in the analysed diagnoses is the study on the degree of adaptability of the open space layout; identifying this can lead to the promotion of different approaches, from radical demolition to conservation. Intermediate, more

advanced solutions are those that have identified specific problems and opportunities and that promote a certain degree of transformation that allows the characteristics of functionalist open space to be adapted to other current design principles. Therefore, exploring the specificity of the critical points of obsolete open spaces, detecting their opportunities for improvement and enhancing those aspects which are effective can contribute to improving the design of urban regeneration processes.

In light of this study, and after demonstrating the relevance of open spaces as drivers for regenerating housing estates, future lines of research should develop further meaningful diagnoses, encouraging a greater level of commitment in the interventions by using this key element of functionalist urban planning. The open spaces should not be the only aspect to consider in the urban regeneration of mass housing estates, but, without any doubt, they should be considered during the development of integrated strategies and processes.

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Tables caption

Table 1. Relationship between accumulated physical problems and quality principles of open space. Compiled by the authors. Accumulated problems based on Moya González (1983), Ferrer i Aixalá (1996), Hall (1997), Turkington *et al.* (2004), Wassenberg (2013) and García Vázquez *et al.* (2016) and quality principles based on Carmona (2018).

Table 2. Three experiences of housing estate regeneration in Spain.

Figures caption

Figure 1. Morphological analysis of the interventions. Transformations of buildings, plots and open space configuration. While the intervention in Zaragoza (rehabilitation) and Madrid (demolition - rehabilitation) does not modify the original plot and open space structure, in La Mina, the demolition and new construction implies a formal transformation of the housing estate. Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 2. Types of diagnosis and types of intervention detected. Source: Own elaboration.

Table 1. Relationship between accumulated physical problems and quality principles of open space.
 Compiled by the authors. Accumulated problems based on Moya González (1983), Ferrer i Aixelá (1996), Hall (1997), Turkington *et al.* (2004), Wassenberg (2013) and García Vázquez *et al.* (2016) and quality principles based on Carmona (2018).

Quality principles											
	Evolving	Diverse	Free	Delineated	Engaging	Meaningful	Social	Balanced	Comfortable	Robust	
Accumulated problems											
Location (physical isolation, including external physical barriers) / Not well connected				•			•				
Monofunctional use / Separation functions											
Lack of facilities and amenities and, sometimes, inflexible amenities					•					•	
Alienating and impersonal physical environment (empty spaces). Repetition and trivialisation of the same type buildings	•	•				•					
Lack of urbanisation									•	•	
Increased number of cars, causing traffic jams and parking problems								•			
Ambiguity on density / intensity							•				
Lack of maintenance of the physical environment									•		
Uncontrollable semi-public and collective spaces			•	•							
Buildings do not have a direct relationship with streets				•							

Table 2. Three experiences of housing estate regeneration in Spain.

	San Cristóbal de los Angeles, Madrid ARI San Cristóbal	4 Pilot Projects, Zaragoza 'Urban Regeneration and Restoration Area' - Urban Complexes of Interest	La Mina, Barcelona Urban Transformation Plan
	1999-2010	2008-2011	2002-2008
No. of dwellings	1,897 (affected)	672 (affected)	2,721 (existing)
HA	42.73	10.78	33.31
Total Public Investment (millions of euros)	42.04	24.70	173.70
Public investment updated according to CPI (2011)	40.74	24.70	165.82
Rate of investment in housing (€/dwelling)	16,055.58	32,250.00	20,580.31
Rate of investment in open space (€/m ²)	24.05	28.04	233.49
Building dimension	Budget: 75%	Budget: 88%	Budget: 34%
Diagnosis	Severe structural pathologies Lack of adaptation to current standards	Lack of adaptation to current standards	Good structural condition Lack of adaptation to current standards
Proposal	Renovation of buildings with severe pathologies and rehabilitation in the remaining cases following energy efficiency and accessibility criteria.	Integral rehabilitation, focusing on accessibility and thermal insulation	Improvement of accessibility at building level Redesign of common spaces
Open space dimension	Budget: 25%	Budget: 12%	Budget: 47%
Diagnosis	Problems related to accessibility and poor conservation	Poor conservation, related to failures to define ownership Lack of parking	Need to replan public spaces due to lack of intensity and diversity. Need to improve connectivity by taking advantage of synergies with the development of the immediate surroundings
Proposal	Improvement of supply facilities at urban level Reurbanisation of open space (furniture, pavements and vegetation)	Improvement of supply facilities at urban level Reurbanisation of the open space (furniture, pavements and vegetation)	New land division Replanning and urbanisation of a new boulevard Reurbanisation of open space Improvement of connections with public transport New facilities and services
Socio-economic dimension			Budget: 15%
Diagnosis	Aging population with low resources New area of concentration of immigrants Need for support during the transformation process	Concentration of aging population and/or with low resources Participation and management difficulty	Security problems
Proposal	Community Development Program (funding is not contemplated in the ARI)	Social support for inhabitants (funding not contemplated in the ARI)	Participating and social plan Work access programme Commercial activation programme
Other			Budget: 4%
Diagnosis		The municipality plan does not consider interventions relating to conservation / renewal.	Poor reputation of the neighbourhood
Proposal		Inclusion in the land-use plan catalogue	Improvement of the external image of the neighbourhood
Source	(Arroyo Castillo, 2010)	(UN-Habitat, 2010a)	(Consorci del Barri de La Mina, 2008)

Transformations on buildings

Transformations on plot structure

Transformations on open space structure

San Cristóbal de los Ángeles, Madrid

4 Pilot Projects (G. Girón), Zaragoza

La Mina, Barcelona

buildings

- demolished buildings
- new buildings
- original buildings
- refurbished buildings
- refurbished buildings (after under study period)

plot structure

- modified plots
- current plot structure

open space structure

- former boundary of open space
- current buildings
- private use plots
- open space

Diagnosis

Problems - opportunity

Low adaptability

High adaptability

Intervention

+ radical transformation

- radical transformation

